

IMPORTANCE OF INNOVATIVE EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN ASTRONOMY

Sayfullaeva Gulkhayo Ikhtiyor Kizi Navoi State Pedagogical Institute, Phd

*Mirzaqandova Sahibjamol Kholmomin's Kizi- student of the Navoi State
Pedagogical Institute*

Key words: interactive methodology, innovative education, innovation, pedagogical technology, information technology, traditional education.

Abstract: This article discusses the importance of innovative educational technologies in the context of advanced education. Information was also given on ways to make education more effective, how to use modern technologies during the lesson.

Today, the interest and attention to the use of interactive methods, innovative technologies, pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process is increasing day by day, one of the reasons for this is that until now, traditional education If students are taught to acquire only ready-made knowledge, modern technologies teach them to search for the acquired knowledge by themselves, to study and analyze independently, and even to draw their own conclusions. In this process, the teacher creates conditions for the development, formation, learning and upbringing of the individual, and at the same time performs the functions of management and guidance. In the process of education, the student becomes the main figure. That is why modern teaching methods - interactive methods, and the role of innovative technologies are extremely important in the training of qualified professionals in higher educational institutions and faculties. Knowledge, experience, and interactive methods of pedagogical technology and pedagogic skills ensure that students acquire knowledgeable, mature skills.

INNOVATION (English innavation) is innovation, innovation. Innovative technologies are innovations and changes in the pedagogical process and the activities of teachers and students, and interactive methods are used in its implementation. Interactive

methods are called group thinking, that is, they are methods of pedagogical influence and are a component of educational content. The uniqueness of these methods is that they are implemented only through the joint activity of pedagogues and students. Such a process of pedagogical cooperation has its own characteristics, which include:

- Forcing the student not to be indifferent during the lesson, to think independently, to create and search;

- Ensuring that students are constantly interested in knowledge during the educational process;

- Increasing the student's interest in knowledge by independently approaching each issue creatively;

- Organization of activities of pedagogue and student-student in cooperation. In the opinion of teachers, researchers, and practitioners studying the issues and problems of pedagogical technologies, pedagogical technology is only related to information technology, and it is necessary to use TSO, computer, distance learning in the teaching process. defined as winter or the use of different techniques. In our opinion, the main basis of the pedagogical technology depends on the technologies selected for the cooperation of the teacher and the student-student to achieve a guaranteed result from the specified goal, that is, used in the teaching process to achieve a guaranteed result according to the goal each educational technology can organize cooperative activities between the teacher and the student, both can achieve a positive result, if the students can think independently, work positively, search, analyze if they can, if they can make their own conclusions, if they can appreciate themselves, the group, and the group can appreciate them, and the teacher can create opportunities and conditions for such activities, in our opinion, this is the basis of the teaching process. Each lesson, topic, educational subject has its own technology, that is, pedagogical technology in the educational process is an individual process, which is directed to one goal based on the needs of the student. is a pedagogical process aimed at providing a pre-planned and guaranteed resultLaw of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education". Innovative pedagogical technologies in the implementation of the "National Personnel

Training Program". The fact that technologicalization of pedagogical activity is a social necessity, that technologicalization of pedagogical activity is a social necessity. arming future teachers with knowledge of the theoretical foundations of modern pedagogical technologies; to have the necessary skills to effectively organize pedagogical processes at a new pedagogical level; the ability to find a way in modern pedagogical technologies, schools, directions, wide variety of ideas; formation of readiness to creatively and methodically perform pedagogic activity; it is said that it is necessary to activate independent work, independent education, self-education, and the desire to constantly improve one's level of expertise.

List of references

1. Sultanova, S. M., Nurmatova, I., Orzigul, Kh. (2021). "Uzbekistan Temir Yullari" JSC "Financial analysis and information system accounting". "Actual issues of evaluating the economic effectiveness of digital and innovative technologies in the transport system of Uzbekistan", 2(1), 137-142.
2. Sultanova, S. M., Nurmatova, I. (2021). Analysis of the tax burden of the railway transport industrial enterprise. BULLETIN OF KHORAZM MAMOON ACADEMY, 5(5), 23-28.
3. Sultanova, S., Kolesnikova, TD, Smolennikova, L., Strelnikova, N. (2021). Generation of an instrument base for analysis of economic processes for the purpose of building a model of spatial development of regions in the context of global challenges. Attended in international conference on economics, management and technologies 2021 (ICEMT 2021), 1(1), 134-145.